

High power density Piezo motors for critical environments

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Abstract

Piezoelectric motors offer many advantages for applications in numerous industrial sectors. The requirements for which these solutions are developed are focused on their main advantages such as non-magnetic and radiation compatibility, high force/volume ratio, good unpowered stall force and low power consumption.

Such applications are typically concerned by exotic working conditions on which the piezoelectric motors still need to improve regarding the technological readiness level. The presence of friction elements, seen as one of the key elements of such actuators, and forecasting their behaviour with relative to the several environments, is one of the improvement areas for the technology. For these motors, the main challenge will be to ensure the nominal performances through a large thermal environment, under cryogenic or high temperature, in air and vacuum environment, or even submitted to high radiation doses.

To explore and validate the good behaviour of the piezoelectric motors, Cedrat Technologies (CTEC) worked on projects to study several designs which will be developed to sustain Aircraft, Space, Defense and Nuclear environmental conditions to improve the repeatability, the reliability and the technological readiness level.

1 AUDACITY Piezo motor – Aircraft application

1.1 Introduction

the actuator developed is an improved inchworm actuator for AUDACITY project, that will need to sustain a very high stall force (500N) in order to ensure the good uplocks behaviour for future landing gear systems. This actuator is composed of two piezo elements, one active clamping system and one extension actuator, and a passive preload mechanism to guarantee the stall force unpowered, at rest. One of the challenge of this design is to make sure that the piezo actuator performances are stable on the whole thermal range (-55..+70°C). The mechanical plays involved require indeed a high machining precision that shall not be perturbed by the thermal effects. This actuator will have one of the best power to mass ratio ever designed in the industry.

1.2 Actuator design

The AUDACITY application aims to fill a gap in piezo motor by maximizing the mass to power ratio of such actuators. In the current state of the art, the required working point is not covered by any of the existing solutions.

An internal trade-off has been performed to evaluate the best potential solution, which took into considerations the main requirements of the application.

1.2.1 Final design architecture

The actuator is using an inchworm based technology which will use an accumulation of several steps in order to move and clamp a high load (500N) at the required speed of 10mm/s. It will simply make this motor the most powerful ever designed.

Figure 1 Inside view of AUDACITY actuator

It consists in one piezo extender to move the mobile part, and one piezo clamp which transfers the blocking force between the passive clamps and the active clamp.

A high precision machining and assembly is needed to guarantee the accurate gap needed between the active and passive clamping elements.

Figure 2 Assembled AUDACITY actuator

The actuation signal will be a trapezoidal shape with a phase shift to ensure the load transfer.

Figure 3 Displacement sequence and driving signals

1.3 Tribological analyses

The friction materials choice is a key element of the AUDACITY inchworm actuator. The pair chosen shall remain with a high friction coefficient with a limited wear in case of continuous friction during the actuations. The high friction coefficient will allow to apply a preload which can be sustained by elastic elements to hold the 500N stall force required. A complete and detailed study has been performed by the AUDACITY partner UNIROMA, and thanks to a dedicated test bench co-designed between UNIROMA and CTEC, the most suitable materials have been embedded in the actuator.

Figure 4 Main instrumentation and sensors embedded in the setup

The friction coefficient measured with the bench is suitable and stable enough for the application, and the inspection performed after the test campaign shows a good behaviour with less than 1mg of measured mass loss and a homogeneous wear on the friction pads.

Figure 5 Friction coefficients and Microscope images of the worn surfaces after 20 mln of sliding cycles

1.4 Conclusion and expected performances

The final performances of the AUDACITY actuator can be summarised in the Table 1

Performances	Values
Stall force	500N
Max weight	< 2kg
Stroke	15mm
Speed	> 9mm/s
Life	130 000 cycles
Temperature	-55 to +71°C

Table 1 AUDACITY Inchworm expected performances

2 Space applications

2.1 Introduction

A second application of the piezo motors is to cover a specific space application need with two different motorization types. One rotary piezo motor is studied to assess the stability for a high thermal range (-80..+50°C) and thermal vacuum environment. Such conditions used to be a major drawback for this solution as the rotary piezo motors working point are highly dependent to temperature and gaseous state. An adjustable preload system has been developed and will then allow to adapt the level of preload between the stator and the rotor. Other improvements are also added to optimize the contact performances between these two key elements. The second piezo motor developed is a linear focus mechanism which will demonstrate the stability of a linear piezo motor using modular stepping piezo actuators (MSPA) in cryogenic vacuum conditions, to complete previous CTEC studies [1].

2.2 Rotary motor definition

2.2.1 Mechanism and thermal stability solution description

The rotary actuator consists of one ultrasonic motor and a preload adjustment system. The motor main drawback was the environment conditions that had to remain stable to ensure the right performances, as a combination of resonance and friction is used.

Figure 6 Rotary motor with preload adjustment system

The active preload system has been balanced to make sure the thermal dilatation does not generate any unplanned load from the APA300ML®.

The rotary motor has been improved by modifying the friction materials between the stator and rotor. By changing the stiffness of the rotor, the preload system has also been optimized. The expected performances of this actuator are summarised in the **Table 2**.

Performances	Values
Max weight	300gm (w/o preload system)
Nominal torque	1 Nm
Nominal Speed	> 50RPM
Life	10 ⁶ cycles
Temperature	-80 to +50°C

Table 2 Rotary motor performances table

2.3 Linear piezo actuator application

2.3.1 Mechanism description

The linear piezo actuator is a stick and slip motor that consists in three Modular Stepping Piezo Actuators (MSPA) fixed at 120° from each other which will, thanks to a flexure guiding system, move the payload with an accurate linear movement.

Figure 7 Linear piezo actuator view

Thanks to the robust preload system, this motor will be able to move 10N for a 8mm stroke. The dynamical performances are validated through a numerical model similar to the one in **Figure 13**. The challenge of this motor is to be able to provide the said performances through vacuum cryogenic conditions. To do so, the actuator will be placed in a cryogenic chamber to validate the behaviour.

2.3.2 Preliminary test results

A first characterisation in a laboratory environment has validated the performances of the actuator which showed a good dynamical behaviour.

Figure 8 Displacement VS time of the linear piezo motor. The measured performances of the motor are shown in **Table 3**.

Performances	Values
Max weight	1700gm
Nominal force	>10N (up to 30N)
Nominal Speed	>10mm/s (up to 25mm/s)
Stroke	8mm (+/-4mm)
Life	10 ⁶ cycles
Temperature	-190 to +25°C

Table 3 Linear motor performance table

3 Nuclear applications

3.1 Introduction

In Nuclear application such as ITER, a MSPA has been developed in order to travel at least 300 km in vacuum, high temperature conditions. It shall work under severe radiation environment. High temperatures are usually an issue with piezo elements that generate additional self-heating in vacuum. Thermal management is then a major topic for this application.

3.2 Design

The design of the MSPA for ITER application take into consideration the radiation, magnetic and thermal constraint in vacuum configuration. Two MSPA are developed for in order to actuate to different axes. The needs in terms of performances are different for the two axes (**Table 4**). The torque, the speed and dimension are the major parameters to fit. Both MSPA are based on APA 40SM[®]. The rotation speed for prism and bracket are obtained with a different diameter of the rotor and also two different excitation signals.

The preliminary performances of both motors are estimated using an electromechanical modelling. The simulated strokes versus time are given below (**Figure 9**). The achievable speed are about 8.6 (for the prism) and 3.8 rpm (for the bracket) using excitation signal frequency set at 320 Hz.

Figure 9 The simulated displacement versus time

Both motors manufactured and assembled are presented below (**Figure 10**). A preliminary test is performed to determine:

- The speed of the motor
- The holding torque
- The heat elevation

Figure 10 The rotary MSPA for a prism and bracket load

A preliminary phase of the testing is the tuning of the excitation signal (frequency and voltage). The tuning phase shows two different signals (for the prism and bracket). For the bracket motor, the optimal signal is obtained at 140 Hz for 1.9 rpm. For the prism, the signal is set at 260 Hz for 6.5 rpm. These performances are obtained in vacuum configuration.

The main constraint during the testing is to measure the temperature due to the self-heating of the piezoelectric material. The most critical case corresponds to use in a vacuum for the prism motor. The temperature at the piezoelectrical material is presented here after (**Figure 11**). The temperature corresponds to three different voltages (power) for a same signal at 260 Hz.

Figure 11 The heat elevation on the piezoelectric material

In steady state, the temperature on the piezoelectric material reaches 176 °C (the limitation of the material according experience is set at 150 °C). The thermal issue due to the

self-heating is still under working by including a thermal draining solution.

3.3 Conclusion

The main performances of the Nuclear MSPA motor are given in the **Table 4**.

Performances	Prism	Bracket
Temperature (°C)	+ 70	+ 70
Radiation (Mgy)	2.5	2.5
Magnetic field (T)	3.5	3.5
Nominal torque (N.mm)	20	100
Nominal Speed (rpm)	6.5	2.0
Life (Km)	300	300
Temperature (°C)	+ 70	+ 70

Table 4 Nuclear MSPA performance and compatibility

4 Miniature piezo motor

4.1 Introduction

Cedrat Technologies aims at increasing the technology readiness level of its piezo motors in areas such as Aircraft, Space, Nuclear and Defence. Due to the high expectations in term of compactness and dynamic behaviour, the limits are endlessly pushed to miniaturize existing devices while keeping reliable performances.

Indeed, a miniature rotative piezo motor has been designed and tested in ambient conditions featuring adequate specifications for a Defence application.

4.2 Development of new miniature MSPA30uXS for Defence application

Thanks to the stick-slip effect [2], MSPA can be used to generate either a linear [3] or a rotary motion [4]. Indeed, the output movement of the load depends on the geometry of the contact interface between the piezo actuator and the load:

- Plane/Plane results in linear motion,
- Plane/Cylinder results in rotational motion.

In this application the MSPA is set up in rotational mode in order to actuate a gear wheel (**Figure 12**). The full device including the piezo actuator, the preload system and the wheel fits in a 23x20x6 mm³ envelope (excluding the demonstration support).

Figure 12 Compact rotative piezo motor designed for Defence application based on APA30uXS®

The dynamic performances of the device are estimated by electromechanical modelling considering main parameters such as the wheel inertia, the actuator stiffness and the friction contact parameters.

The numerical model results (**Figure 13**) shows the backlash phenomenon that is frequently observed on the MSPA between each step. Since the average speed of the actuator is directly connected to the step size of the motor, the backlash must be minimized by tuning precisely the frequency of the actuation signal. This optimization is generally performed during the testing phase with a dedicated test bench.

Figure 13 Simulated MSPA30uXS stroke versus time

The testing phase includes:

- Holding torque at rest (not alimented),
- Actuation speed versus torque curves.

On the five prototypes. Due to the dissymetry of the preloading effect, the piezo motor presents a better behaviour in the counter clockwise direction than the clockwise direction (**Figure 14**). The optimal frequency for rotational speed was found at 740 Hz. However since it corresponds to the system electromechanical resonance, the system was quite unstable in terms of repeatability. Lowering the signal frequency to 475 Hz increased the stability of the motion along the output torque available.

These load curve shapes are characteristic in MSPA applications because the maximum transmissible torque is limited by the preload set up in the system.

Figure 14: Test load curves of the piezo devices

4.3 Conclusion

The final performances of the miniature MSPA devices are given in the **Table 5**.

Performances	Value	Unit
Stroke	360	°
Holding torque	1800	mN.mm
Blocked torque @475Hz	650	mN.mm
Maximum speed @475 Hz	2	rad/s
Voltage range	[-20, 150]	V
Current	150	mA
Envelope	23x20x6	mm ³

Table 5 Miniature MSPA30uXS tested performances

This miniature piezo motor design is being enhanced to withstand at least the following environmental specifications:

- Static acceleration: up to 200g.
- Sine vibrations: up to 20g (until 100 Hz).
- Random vibrations: up to 20g RMS over the frequency range [20; 2000] Hz.
- Chocs: 500g SRS 10kHz.
- Operational temperature range: [-55; 70] °C.

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6 Literature

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